

Morphing-Based Reharmonization with VAE: Reducing Dissonance with Consonance-Based Loss Function

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Abstract

This study proposes a model to reduce dissonant chords in morphing-based reharmonization using a variational autoencoder (VAE). The conventional morphing of chords generates dissonance because the generated results are supplemented by the surrounding learning data in the latent space without considering consonance. Therefore, this study focuses on degrees of dissonance that can be calculated from pitch intervals. We define an ideal consonance degree based on the dissonance degree, and we implement a dissonance penalty as a simple network structure by adding nodes to the VAE so that a co-occurrence vector of pitch interval computed from each chord tone approaches the ideal consonance degree. Our objective evaluation demonstrates that the number of standard triads increased compared to the conventional VAE morphing method when the model was used. In addition, the number of non-standard and dissonant chords decreased through our model.

1 Introduction

Reharmonization is an essential technique for arranging music, especially in jazz. Musicians select different chord progressions for the same melody to generate different impressions of the music. Reharmonization is not an easy technique for beginner musicians to master. Thus, automatic reharmonization is highly desirable, as it would enable anyone to enjoy playing the same songs in a variety of styles. However, the main barrier in designing an automatic reharmonization system is the controllability of the musical style (i.e., controlling the style of generated chord progressions). The controller should be intuitive, musically understandable, and user-friendly for people with no musical knowledge.

The representation of chord progressions in the latent space is suitable for a controller because this approach allows each chord progression to represent a point. It is easy for users to search for their preferred chord progressions by referring to reharmonized chord progressions. They can also obtain various reharmonizations among many reharmonization instances by morphing.

Morphing is a technique for generating medial data between two given instances. Although morphing is generally done in image processing, the morphing of melodies [1], chords, basslines, and drum patterns [2, 3] has also been conducted. Morphing two musical instances is commonly performed by MusicVAE [4, 2] and MIDI-VAE [5]. Several approaches have been proposed to variationally harmonize melodies, such as SurpriseNet [6] and Translating Melody to Chord [7]. SurpriseNet [6] generated a varied chord progression by allowing the user to add a condition and a surprise contour to the melody. In [7], a regularized variational transformer increased chord diversity and allowed more explicit control over chord output. A method for morphing reharmonized chord progressions was developed in [8] using an LSTM-variational autoencoder (VAE). In that method, intermediate chord progressions were generated by interpolating. However, in these studies, the results were

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Figure 1: Network structure.

appropriately supplemented by the surrounding data in the latent space, and the consonance of each chord was not considered in their models.

In this study, we consider adding a factor to the loss function to reduce the dissonance of chord tones. We combine a dissonance penalty to the usual loss of a VAE, with the aim of constraining the loss so that chord tones become more consonant. This is accomplished by modifying the simple network structure and adding nodes for a co-occurrence vector of the pitch interval to the VAE network. By computing the loss between the co-occurrence vector of the pitch interval and the ideal degree of consonance, we expect to enable control of each chord tone to approach consonance. We manage the harmonization of chord simultaneity through the model.

2 Generation Algorithm

We add a mechanism to the VAE to reduce the dissonance. The dissonance degree of music interval can be computed in [9]. We can regard reducing the level of dissonance as bringing each chord tone closer to consonance, so we define the ideal degree of consonance. We implement it as a simple network structure with additional nodes for the co-occurrence of pitch interval to approach ideal consonance during training.

2.1 Network Structure

A VAE is a neural network that acquires characteristics for expressing data. Moreover, it assumes a multivariate standard normal distribution for latent variables [10]. Importantly, VAE models generate specific data based on an abstract representation of the latent variable. For this study, we assume latent variable z , which represents the chord progression character. As usual, we let z obey the multivariate standard Gaussian distribution of the mean vector $\mathbf{0}$, and covariance matrix I . Further, we use \mathbf{x} as song data and z as the latent variable corresponding to \mathbf{x} to maximize the marginal likelihood $p_\theta(\mathbf{x})$ for training the VAE. We also make a distribution from $q_\phi(z|\mathbf{x})$, which generates a latent variable distribution in the VAE. Terms θ and ϕ are sets of model parameters of the encoder and the decoder, respectively. A conditional VAE (CVAE) [11] improves the VAE by conditioning the encoder and decoder to y . We treat the chord style as a controllable condition. The variational lower bound of the log-likelihood is expressed by the following equation:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \phi; \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \mathbb{E}_{q_\phi(z|\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})} [\log p_\theta(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}, z) + \log p(\mathbf{y})] - D_{KL}[q_\phi(z|\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})||p(z)]. \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 displays the network structure. We regard song \mathbf{x} as a chord progression sequence. The onset series of note pitches is represented in units of quarter notes. The length of the sequences for

Figure 2: For dissonance reduction, the co-occurrence vectors of pitch interval are replaced by the ideal degree of consonance at target during learning.

LSTM is 16 because we use a four-bar chord progression. Let be x at t -th quarter note as x_t . We treat the four octaves of C2 to B5 to add nodes having melodic and harmonic information. It should be noted that the number of notes contained in a chord is limited to five, and one note is represented as a one-hot vector, which includes the silent state. Accordingly, the one-hot vector has 49 ($12 \times 4 + 1$) dimensions. A melody is also represented as a one-hot vector, like a chord. We add a node with a 12-dimensional chroma vector.

We combine these nodes with nodes for the co-occurrence vector of pitch intervals. A co-occurrence vector of pitch intervals is calculated from the multiplication of two pitch class values of the chroma vector. The values are multiplied together, and then the chroma vector is shifted in the pitch direction. The t -th co-occurrence vector of pitch intervals is represented as 144 nodes. Thus, x_t is represented as a combination of five one-hot vectors representing chords, a one-hot vector for the melody, a chroma vector, and a co-occurrence vector of pitch interval. Thus, the number for the input nodes for x_t is $49 \times 5 + 49 + 12 + 144 = 450$. The encoder and decoder contain two LSTM layers. All have a bidirectional structure, and their hidden size is 128. The output h_{end} of the encoder is combined with the style condition vector represented as a 37-dimensional one-hot vector. They are converted into a 64-dimensional latent variable z . The latent variable is then combined with the style condition vector and converted to 128 dimensions through the fully connected layers. Then, they are input into LSTM decoder as h_0 . The output of the LSTM decoder goes through the fully connected layer, which maps the output of the LSTM to the sequence length.

2.2 Dissonance Penalty

During training, we replace the co-occurrence vector of the target with an ideal degree of consonance. Because the output of the model also includes the co-occurrence vector, we aim for a model in which the two notes ideally co-occur by computing the loss with the target. In other words, as the loss decreases, we expect the generated chord tones to become more consonant. Figure 2 shows an image of the dissonance penalty the t -th output and the t -th target.

The degree of consonance between two pitch classes is based on an interval of semitones concerning the dissonance curve [9]. Each value indicates how the degree of dissonance changes between two notes and is calculated as follows. First, we assume that the i th harmonic of the first note is f_{1i} , the frequency of the j th harmonic of the second note is f_{2j} , and their respective volumes are v_{1i} and v_{2j} . Then, let x_{ij} be the pitch defined by f_{1i} and f_{2j} and let v_{ij} be the values defined as v_{1i} and v_{2j} . The dissonance degree D of the compound note is defined as follows:

$$D = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} d(x_{ij}, v_{ij}). \quad (2)$$

Although a chroma vector ignores octave information, we process the original piano roll for four octaves, meaning D is calculated as the fourth harmonic. The degree of consonance C is as follows:

$$C = \exp(-D). \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Dissonance curve and the degree of consonance C .

Figure 3 presents the dissonance curve and the degree of consonance. From the figure, it is evident that the dissonant intervals (minor second, major second, major seventh, and minor seventh), and the augmented fourth degree are lower. In contrast, the unison and perfect fifth intervals are higher.

2.3 Chord Morphing

We can generate a chord progression by decoding from a style condition vector and a latent variable. Assuming that the latent variables of the two songs are z_1 and z_2 , the latent variable z of the morphed song is expressed as follows:

$$z = (1 - \alpha)z_1 + \alpha z_2, \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. Finally, we obtain the chord progression by decoding z and the style condition.

3 Results

The models were trained on 1,531 chord progressions from data containing common patterns [12, 13], and the chords were manually reharmonized by a professional musician. Five or more chord progression styles were assigned to a melody, which resulted in a total of 37 styles. All song keys were transposed to either C major or C minor. We did not consider any changes to the dynamics in the songs. Further, we split notes that were longer than quarter notes, and we omitted notes that were shorter than quarter notes. The model was trained with a mini-batch size of 32 and 20,000 epochs. In the loss function, we used cross-entropy loss for each feature node. We used Adaptive moment estimation (Adam) [14] as the optimizer. We set the learning rate to 0.001, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.99$, and $\lambda = 1e - 08$. In addition, we incorporated KL divergence annealing. The weights were added by $4e - 04$ for each batch training until they were greater than 1. Because the decoded results were $[0, 1]$, we found the maximum value of each one-hot vector node, and we output the corresponding note number or rest, respectively. Each velocity was set to 100 to allow for conversion to a MIDI signal.

3.1 Objective Evaluation

For the evaluation experiment, we used the MIDI data from 84 melodies, and we analyzed a total of 11,400 chord progressions. The morphed chord progressions were obtained by varying α in increments of 0.25 for song z_1 and the other styles z_2 . Since the conditions allowed us to set the style of the song, we generated each chord progression in three styles (s_1 to s_3): style s_1 for z_1 ; style s_2 for z_2 ; s_3 was a 50/50 mix of s_1 and s_2 , represented as $s_3 = (s_1 + s_2)/2$. To confirm the

Table 1: Extracted jSymbolic Features

Feature name	Description
Standard Triads	A fraction of all simultaneously sounding pitch groups that are major or minor triads.
Diminished and Augmented Triads	A fraction of all simultaneously sounding pitch groups that are diminished or augmented triads.
Dominant Seventh Chords	A fraction of all simultaneously sounding pitch groups that are dominant seventh chords.
Seventh Chords	A fraction of all simultaneously sounding pitch groups that are seventh chords.
Non-Standard Chords	A fraction of a simultaneously sounding pitch groups that consist of two or more pitch classes. They are neither a major triad, a minor triad, nor a seventh chord.
Complex Chords	A ratio of all simultaneously sounding notes that contain four or more notes.
Vertical Dissonance Ratio	A ratio of vertical dissonant intervals (seconds, tritones, and sevenths) to all vertical consonant intervals (unisons, thirds, fourths, fifths, sixths, and octaves).

effectiveness of our consonance calculation structure, we used the LSTM-VAE as the baseline for comparison [8], excluding co-occurrence vectors of the pitch interval.

We conducted an objective evaluation with chords and vertical interval features extracted by jSymbolic 2.2 [15]. Here, we extracted the features listed in Table 1. We expected higher values in the proposed model for standard triads, diminished and augmented triads, dominant seventh chords and seventh chords, which are all commonly used chords. In comparison, non-standard chords, complex chords, and vertical dissonance ratio values should be low values.

Figures 4 and 5 show that the violin plots of common chord patterns (standard triads, diminished and augmented triads, dominant seventh chords, and seventh chords), non-standard chords, and complex chords, as well as the vertical dissonance ratio. To evaluate the reconstructed piano roll results for 380 pieces of training data, we calculated the cosine similarity at each time. Our comparison method obtained an average of 0.913 (standard deviation: 0.270), and the proposed method also achieved 0.913 (standard deviation: 0.270). The reconstruction performance of the training data was almost the same. These results suggest that the number of standard triads increased with the proposed method. Another notable point is that the proposed method produced fewer non-standard chords, complex chords, and vertical dissonance ratios. From these results, it can be deduced that some of the chords (such as non-standard chords and complex chords) were improved and changed to standard triads. This suggests that the use of a consonance template provides some assistance to the model during training.

However, the co-occurrence vector could not distinguish between five and seven semitones. This is because the shift of the chroma vector is cyclic; shifting five semitones upwards is the same as shifting seven semitones downwards. Although we assumed the degree of consonance considering four-octave differences, the co-occurrence vector did not recognize changes in octaves. In the future, the co-occurrence vector will need to manage intervals greater than one octave.

3.2 Generated Samples

We conducted morphing between z_1 and z_2 , as shown in Figure 6². These chord progressions are an arrangement by add9 and simple chords for the melody of *Twinkle Twinkle Little Star*.

Figure 7 presents the results of chord morphing for $\alpha = 0.5$. With the comparison method, the chord tones were unnaturally reduced in the second and fourth bars. However, the proposed method generated a progression while keeping the original add9. These results are preferable to the chord

²Our morphing results are available at <https://uemaik.org/reharmodemo>

Figure 4: Results of common chord patterns.

Figure 5: Results of non-standard chords, complex chords, and dissonance ratio.

progression that includes add9, because the style condition of add9 was generated at $\alpha = 0.5$. According to the jSymblic features, the vertical dissonance ratio for the comparison method was 0.2118, and that for the standard triads was 0.25. The proposed method had the vertical dissonance ratio of 0.1664 and standard triads of 0.4688. This indicates that the number of standard triads increased while the number of non-standard and dissonant chords decreased.

The results of morphing with s_1 and $\alpha = 1.0$ are displayed in Figure 8. Because this result was reconstructed from z_2 only, we can regard it as a style transformation of the z_2 chord progression. However, the comparison method produced unstable bass notes, and generated unnatural chords in the second and fourth bars. With the proposed method, we found some add9 chords, although the chords suddenly became triads in the fourth bar. There was also a noticeable increase in the number of standard triads, although the number of non-harmonic notes that provided variation in the reharmonization could be decreased by increasing the consonance. Based on the jSymblic features,

Melody $\text{♩} = 120$

Z_1

Z_2

Figure 6: First four bars of trained songs. Top: Original melody (*Twinkle Twinkle Little Star*). Middle: Chord progression arranged by add9 z_1 . Bottom: Simple chord progression z_2 .

(a) Comparison

(b) Proposal

Figure 7: Morphing results of $\alpha = 0.5$ between add9 and simple arrangement styles. Style condition is set to $s_3 = (s_1 + s_2)/2$.

(a) Comparison

(b) Proposal

Figure 8: Morphing results of s_1 and $\alpha = 1.0$ between add9 and simple arrangement styles. We can regard this as a style transformation of the z_2 chord progression.

the vertical dissonance ratio for the comparison method was 0.5062, and that for the non-standard chord was 0.9375. In contrast, the proposed method had a vertical dissonance ratio of 0.2314 and a non-standard chord of 0.5312. Although the results of the proposed method were not desirable, it can be seen that dissonance chords were reduced more in the proposed method than in the comparison method, as well as non-standard chords.

4 Conclusions

In this study, we addressed morphing-based reharmonization by reducing dissonance with a consonance-based loss function. We compared the interval vector of pitch classes with the degree of consonance during the training of the model. The experimental results confirmed that our model increased the number of standard triads and decreased the number of non-standard and dissonant chords by considering consonance.

Although we could control the style condition, we were not able to evaluate whether or not the target style had been achieved. Accordingly, a blind listening test should be conducted in the future. In addition, this model does not fully address cadence. Currently, the chord progression is interrupted every four bars and consists of several cadences, such as perfect authentic cadence, half cadence, and deceptive cadence. Therefore, these should be examined in future studies.

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